

D5.1 Dossier of the Project Visual Identity and Branding

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¹ PU = Public

PP = Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)

RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)

CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

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Summary

Begonia Project

Europe is embarking on a transformative endeavour to modernise digital information usage, with a focus on enhancing the efficiency, sustainability, and connectivity of our energy and transportation sectors. At the core of this initiative lies the development of advanced Operational Digital Platforms (ODPs) that transcend national boundaries, leveraging state-of-the-art technologies such as data sharing, cloud computing, and network connectivity.

The BEGONIA Project is an EU-funded Coordination and Support Action that aims to expedite this digital transformation in the energy and transport sectors, analysing the most promising solutions and providing information to the European Commission to set up and fund future works project(s).

BEGONIA has the goal of identifying, studying and preparing the development of Operational Digital Platforms (ODPs) across different EU countries, starting from the identification of 10 cross-border and possibly cross-sector (energy and transport) use cases, meticulously shortlisting three based on predefined criteria, and evaluating their impacts through proof-of-concept implementation of their ODPs.

Summary of the Deliverable

This document outlines the processes and outcomes involved in establishing the project's visual identity and public image, essential for effective communication with stakeholders throughout its development. Initial research and brainstorming were conducted to identify Begonia's defining characteristics and target audience. Key principles guiding visual identity creation include the focus on data and digital technologies, recognition of the project's European importance, its cross-border and cross-sector nature, and the necessity of transparency in research, particularly given its strategic implications at the EU level. Starting from these principles, and with a technical audience in mind, all visuals and designs, ranging from logo selection and colour palette to templates and website style presented in this report, have been created.

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Table of Acronyms

Acronyms	Description
CA	Consortium Agreement
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
T5.1	Task 5.1
WP(s)	Work Package(s)
ODPs	Operational Digital Platforms

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1. Introduction

1.1. Begonia Project

The aim of the BEGONIA Project is to expedite the European digital transformation by analysing promising solutions and providing recommendations to the European Commission. Specifically, the project focuses on identifying, studying, and preparing the development of ODPs in the energy and transport sectors across various EU countries, with the goal of facilitating the setup and funding of future projects.

1.2. Work Package 5

Work Package 5 -Stakeholders' engagement, Dissemination and Knowledge transfer- runs throughout the 27 months of the project and interacts with all other Work Packages (WPs) with multiple objectives.

First of all, Work Package 5 plans and carries out the Communication and Dissemination of Begonia. The Communication and Dissemination includes the definition of the project's visual identity to support the internal and external dissemination activities, and the implementation of a series of actions that will facilitate the engagement of the community of experts, including a website platform.

Secondly, this Work Package has the goal of creating a community of experts to gather inputs and feedback, find partners, and feed information to all WPs where necessary. The creation of the stakeholder community allows the gathering of necessary inputs and feedback from experts, industry representatives, and relevant stakeholders in order to feed vital information for the development of all the operative Work Packages (WP2, WP3, and WP4).

Finally, WP5 will carry out a know-how transfer of the projects' conclusions to the Commission for the definition of the new calls for project(s) and, in the final months of the project, to the entities awarded the new project(s), providing information and support in the initial phases.

1.3. Task 5.1

This deliverable presents the results of activities that have been carried out in the context of a broader Task, namely Task 5.1 (T5.1).

This Task has the purpose of setting up the work of the whole Work Package 5, having several objectives, developed in parallel to ensure consistency:

- Define and implement the project Visual Identity.
- Draft the project Communication and Dissemination plan.
- Define a strategy to approach stakeholders to be included in a community to engage with throughout the project, both to provide feedback and inputs to all work packages and allow more transparency.
- Identify the most relevant stakeholders to be involved.
- Define a strategy to facilitate the know-how transfer of the project conclusions.
- Design and set up the project website and a platform to facilitate the stakeholders' engagement and knowledge transfer.

This deliverable describes the process and outcomes of the activities carried out to achieve the first goal of T5.1: the definition of the project's visual identity.

2. Begonia Visual Identity

Visual identity is pivotal for the communication and dissemination of a project - both external and internal.

To reach an equal understanding and awareness throughout all the communication efforts, it is necessary to design and implement a visual identity that is at the same time unique and effective to provide a clear but simple message of what Begonia stands for and what are its goals.

This is achieved by defining proper colours, icons, fonts and languages, in line with the project's principles, that are used to vehiculate the purpose of the project to the target stakeholders.

The definition of the visual identity had clear objectives, interconnected one with the other:

- Definition of the project colours and style.
- Design of the project logo.
- Design of the project's main document templates (Word and PowerPoint).
- Definition of the graphic elements to be integrated into the project website.

To ensure consistency, a first research and brainstorming activity has been carried out to identify the main characteristics of the project and the desired audience, in order to shape a visual identity that is in line with the communication activities that will follow.

2.1. Preliminary research

All visual identity elements, from the colours and style to the logo and the consequent graphic elements have the purpose of supporting the communication of the project to the relevant stakeholders that can be engaged throughout the development of the project and for any of the ones that can be interested in its outcomes.

To this end, in the first stages of the project, a preliminary research and brainstorming activity has been carried out to identify the defining traits of Begonia, considering its characteristics and targeted audience.

Due to its nature, Begonia has some key elements that distinguish it and that have been selected to guide the visual identity creation:

- **Data and Digital technologies** | Clear focus on data and data-driven solutions.
- **European** | The significant strategic impact that its outcomes can have at the European level.
- **Cross-border and cross-sector** | The transnational (cross-border) and/or sector integration (cross-sector, namely energy and transport) nature of the solutions to be studied.
- **Transparency** | The necessity of guaranteeing transparency in the research to be carried out due to the strategic impact that the project conclusions can have at the EU level and the relevance of the investment that will follow.

These elements were brought into mind maps and mood boards and have been the start of the Visual Identity discussions that led to the definition of Logos and colours.

Figure 1: Mood board for the visual identity

2.2. Begonia Logo and Colours

Starting from the elements of the preliminary research, the Begonia logo has been designed taking into account the most important elements characterising the project, in order to make it recognizable and define its core principles through a combination of shapes and colours. Different logos have been proposed to the consortium (all options can be found in Annex I).

Figure 2: Main inspirational elements for the Begonia logo

The final colour combination and Logo selection have been further influenced by the European strategic nature of the project, which led to the choice of the European flag-inspired blue and yellow as the main colours. Starting from these, the complete colour palette and the final version of the logo have been created. The colours and the Logo are meant to underline and represent core aspects of the project, especially the data-driven and European nature of it.

Figure 3: Begonia main colour palette

Figure 4: Begonia main logo on blue background

Begonia as a name is written with a modern and technical font that shows innovation. In principle, the logo with a blue background should be used. If it is not possible to use the main logo due to colour characteristics in applications, there are also two one-colour variations.

Figure 5: Begonia one-colour logos

2.3. Visual language

The visual language plays a crucial role in the communication strategy of the Begonia project, whose primary aim is to establish a network of technical stakeholders and interested parties, to be involved in its activities with different degrees of participation.

Graphic elements play a significant role in social media communication and brand representation, demanding both creativity and clarity to simplify complex information while aligning with Begonia's innovative design ethos. All visual motifs, including

symbols, images, and animations, adhere to this cohesive visual identity outlined in the preceding sections.

As a result, similar to the logo, the graphic elements and styles will be designed to capture the attention of a technical audience and convey Begonia's identity effectively, ensuring high recognizability. This visual language is characterized by modernity and high contrast, reflecting technical innovation in the data, energy and transport sectors alongside its distinctly European essence, when possible.

Figure 6: Examples of visual elements created for the Project website

Some additional visual elements have been included in the Word and PowerPoint templates and website style defined in the context of the visual identity, presented in the following section.

2.4. Font, templates and website style

The Begonia style guide defines not only the brand representation itself but also the colour range and all additional graphic elements to be followed for virtual/printed applications will be made.

To further underline the characteristics of the project, a modern and clean font has been selected, namely the **Open Sans**. This font shall be used in all applications, including Word documents, PowerPoints and the website.

The templates created for PowerPoint and Word documents follow the principles described above and are presented in the Figures below.

Figure 7: Begonia Word template

Figure 8: Begonia PowerPoint template

Finally, the website design will follow the same style and be consistent with the principles described, with the European, open, innovative and connective nature of the project that is highlighted by all the graphical elements. Some examples of the muck-up website design are presented below as an example (the texts have to be taken only as an example).

Figure 9: Project website mock-up with graphic elements and visuals

2.5. Project tagline

As guiding principles for the definition of the project's claim or tagline, the decision was made to opt for a short statement that emphasizes key aspects of the project's fundamental goals and focus. Consequently, the phrase "Digital Solutions for Energy & Transport" was formulated.

By emphasizing "Digital Solutions," the tagline highlights the project's commitment to leveraging digital technologies to address challenges within the energy and transport sectors. Furthermore, the inclusion of "Energy & Transport" ensures that the tagline effectively communicates the project's specific areas of interest, facilitating understanding and resonance with the target stakeholders. The tagline may be accompanied by other claims during the prosecution of the project if a more specific focus in certain areas is made evident in the research work carried out.

3. Conclusions

The BEGONIA Project aims to accelerate the digital transformation in Europe by analysing and recommending solutions to the European Commission, specifically focusing on Operational Digital Platforms.

Task 5.1 involves several parallel activities to set up the activities of Work Package 5 that deal with the Stakeholders' Engagement, Dissemination, and Knowledge Transfer activities of the project, among which the definition and implementation of the project's visual identity presented in this report.

Visual identity is critical for both internal and external project communication and dissemination. A clear, unique visual identity helps convey Begonia's goals effectively to stakeholders. Key components include colours, the project logo, graphics, and fonts, aligned with the project's principles.

Initial research and brainstorming activities were conducted to identify Begonia's defining traits and target audience. Key elements such as data and digital technologies, European significance, cross-border and cross-sector integration, and transparency were identified to guide visual identity creation.

The Begonia logo and colour scheme were designed based on project characteristics, emphasizing its data-driven and European nature. The final logo features blue and yellow, inspired by the European flag, representing core aspects of the project.

To guarantee consistency and recognisability, the same concepts have been followed for the whole project's visual language, including the choice of the Font, the design of the Templates, and the Website Style.

In conclusion, the defined visual identity has the ambition to align with Begonia's goals and objectives, facilitating effective communication and dissemination throughout the project's duration.

Annex I – Logos Options

Several logo options have been presented to the consortium following common core principles but with different specifics in mind. The main inspirational elements are indicated in the Figure below:

Figure 10: Inspirational elements common for all Logo options

From these, three final options have been proposed. The taglines were added before the definition of the final version, hence they should be taken only as an example.

Figure 11: Begonia Logo final options